

Burnout and its Drivers among Medical Doctors in Specialty Training in Jos University Teaching Hospital, Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

Background: Burnout is a harmful health event that ensues when a worker's ability to cope with work is diminished following a prolonged period of unhealthy interaction between him/her and the work environment. The burden of the problem among doctors in further training in this part of the world is not known. Hence, this study assessed the level of burnout and its drivers among resident doctors in Jos University Teaching Hospital, Plateau State, Nigeria.

Methodology: This was a cross sectional study conducted among resident doctors using the Maslach Burnout Inventory tool, comprising the Emotional Exhaustion, Depersonalization, and Personal Accomplishment dimensions to assess the level of burnout. SPSS version 23 was used for data analysis with crude and adjusted odds ratios as well as 95% confidence interval presented as point and interval estimates of the effects of the explanatory variables on the level of burnout. A p-value of 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: The mean age of the 112 study participants was 30.0 ± 4.3 years with 67 (59.8%) being 34 years and below. The prevalence of burnout in all the three subscales was 9.8% while 10 (8.9%) had high level of burnout on the Emotional Exhaustion subscale, 32 (28.5%) on the Depersonalization subscale and 39 (34.8%) had high level of burnout on the Personal Achievement subscale. Increasing duration of training was identified as the sole factor significantly associated with an increased risk of burnout (AOR: 1.6; 95% CI: 1.107–2.313; $p=0.012$).

Conclusion: This study brought to light significant level of burnout cutting across emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal achievement subscales among resident doctors with longer duration of training being the sole driver of burnout.

Keywords: Burnout, Emotional Exhaustion, Depersonalization, Personal Achievement, Residency

Introduction

Burnout is a phenomenon resulting from prolonged exposure to emotional and interpersonal stressors in the work-place.^{1,2,3} It is an occupational syndrome associated with interpersonal conflicts, dysfunctional personality traits, or cognitions and faulty coping patterns comprising of three distinguished features relating to feelings of energy loss or emotional exhaustion (EE), cynicism or depersonalization (DP), and professional inefficacy or reduced personal accomplishment (PA).^{2,3,4,5} Burnout is a maladaptive work-related condition with a high prevalence among physicians and associated with an increased prevalence of suicide, divorce, depression, loss of income, and exhibition of disruptive behaviors in the work place.^{6,7,8,9} Residency is a period of specialty training in the various fields of medicine involving tutelage, competency training and certification examination.¹⁰ The structure of the training is inherently demanding and draining mentally, physically and emotionally putting this group at risk of burnout. In addition, there is dearth of empirical evidence on the level of burnout among medical doctors in the this clime.^{10,11} In view of this, it became imperative to assess the level of burnout and its drivers among medical doctors in specialty training in Jos University Teaching Hospital as a way of generating home-grown information for action.

Methodology

Study setting

This study was conducted among medical doctors in residency training in Jos University Teaching Hospital (JUTH), a tertiary health institution established in 1975.¹² The Hospital is located in Jos North Local Government Area (LGA) of Plateau State, North central Nigeria with a bed capacity of 600. It offers a variety of specialized treatment services in the aspects of healthcare, research and training and serves as a referral hub to the surrounding states in the north central, parts of north western and north eastern Nigeria.¹³ Being a tertiary health facility, JUTH has the following training departments; surgery, internal medicine, obstetrics and gynecology, pediatrics, community

medicine, radiology, ophthalmology, pathology, laboratory medicine, otorhinolaryngology, anesthesia, psychiatry and dentistry among others.¹³

Study population

The study population comprised of all resident doctors undergoing residency training in JUTH at the time of the study.

Criteria for inclusion in the study

All resident doctors in specialty training in all the departments in Jos University Teaching Hospital who gave consent for participation and were physically present at the time of the study.

Study design

This was a cross sectional study design employed to the assess the levels of burnout and its drivers among doctors in residency training in Jos University Teaching Hospital between December 2019 and May 2020.

Sample size estimation

The sample size for this study was determined using the Cochran formula for sample size determination for a cross sectional study.¹⁴ Where n is the minimum sample size, Z is the standard normal deviate at 95% confidence interval (1.96), q is the complementary probability ($1 - p$), d is the precision of the study set at 0.05 and p is the prevalence of burnout in all three dimensions as 6.3% from a previous similar study.¹⁵ This gave a minimum sample size of 100 after addition of 10% to cater for non, poor and incomplete responses.

Sampling technique

A cluster approach to sampling was employed where all eligible resident doctors from all the 16 departments were provided the questionnaire for self-administration through their respective chief residents with all the filled questionnaires returned within 3 days through the same chief residents to the research team. A total 134 questionnaires were returned out of which 112 were completely filled.

Data collection

A paper-based self-administered Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) questionnaire was adopted and

used in this study.¹⁶ The Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) is a standardized tool designed to measure burnout and is widely used in research consisting of three subscales: Emotional Exhaustion (EE), Depersonalization (DP), and Personal Accomplishment (PA). Each of the subscales uses a 7-point Likert scale for eliciting responses ranging from “never” (=0) to “daily” (=6). The EE and DP subscales has 7 stem questions respectively while the PA subscale had 8 stem questions. The questionnaires were given to the chief residents of all the respective departments based on the eligible number of respondents in each department. The chief residents helped in the retrieval of all the filled questionnaires which were subsequently collected by the research assistants. Upon receipt of all the filled questionnaires from departmental focal persons, the trained research assistant reviewed all the questionnaires for completeness and appropriateness of the responses as required. The data collection spanned a period of four weeks. Written informed consent was obtained prior to the administration of the questionnaires and confidentiality and anonymity of the information provided by the participants were assured and maintained.

Grading of response

The assessment of the level of burnout was done using a grading system from the Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) which had 3 subscales: Emotion Exhaustion (EE), Depersonalization (DP) and Personal Accomplishment (PA) using a 7-point Likert scale ranging from “never” (=0) to “daily” (=6) with the lowest score of 0 and the highest score of 6 in each section for a 22 item questions. The EE and DP subscales had 7 stem questions respectively with maximum attainable scores of 42 for each while the PA subscale had 8 stem questions with a maximum attainable score of 48. For EE subscale, a score of 30 and above was considered high level burnout, 18– 29 moderate level burnout and 17 and less low-level burnout. For DP subscale, a score of 12 and greater was considered high level burnout, 6 – 11 moderate level burnout and 5 and less low-level burnout. For the PA subscale, a score of 33 and less was considered as high-level burnout, 34–39 moderate

level burnout and 40 and above low-level burnout. A high score in EE and DP subscales even with a low score in PA was adjudged burnout in all the subscales.¹⁶

Data analysis

The data obtained were processed and analyzed using SPSS version 23 where socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents such as sex, marital status, religion, department of training, hours worked per day etc. were categorized appropriately and presented with frequency and percentage. Quantitative measures such age, number of calls taken in a month, number of years spent in residency training and score of the subscales for assessment of burnout were subjected to normality test using Kolmogorov Smirnov test. Age and hours worked per day fulfilled the assumption of normality and therefore mean \pm standard deviation was used as summary indices. Other quantitative measures did not fulfil the assumptions of normality and as such median and interquartile range were employed as the summary indices for them. The primary outcome variable in the study is the burnout in all the subscales categorized as yes or no while the secondary outcome variable is the level of burnout in the different subscales of Emotional Exhaustion (EE), Depersonalization (DP) and Personal Accomplishment (PA) categorized as low, moderate and high levels each. A multivariable analysis approach was used to determine the factors influencing burnout. All explanatory variables were individually entered into a binary logistic regression model to generate crude odds ratios (CORs) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs). Subsequently, all variables were included simultaneously in a multiple logistic regression model. Multicollinearity was assessed using the variance inflation factor (VIF) and tolerance values of the independent variables. Tolerance values of 0.10 and below and VIF values of 10 and above were taken as presence of collinearity.¹⁷ The tolerance values in the study ranged from 0.58 to 0.92 and VIF values ranged from 1.12–1.19, indicating no collinearity between the variables. Adjusted odds ratios and 95% confidence intervals were generated and used as point and interval estimates of the measure of effect of the

explanatory variables predicting the burnout respectively with each variable in the model adjusting for the other.

Ethical considerations

Ethical clearance was obtained from Jos University Teaching Hospital Health Research Ethics Committee (JUTH/DCS/IREC/127/XXX/2136). Written informed consent was obtained from all the respondents with confidentiality and anonymity of their responses assured and maintained.

Results

A total of 112 resident doctors participated in this study with a mean age of 30.0 ± 4.3 years and 67 (59.8%) being 34 years and below. Eighty-five (75.9%) of the respondents were males and 68 (60.7%) were married. With regards years spent in training, 80 (71.4%) had been in training for 3 years while 75 (67.0%) of them had been on call duty for 4 or more times in a month. Table 1

In relation to the assessment of burnout, 10 (8.9%) of the respondents had high level of burnout on the Emotional Exhaustion subscale while 66 (58.9%) had low level of burnout. In the Depersonalization and Personal Accomplishment subscale, 32 (28.5%) and 39 (34.8%) had high levels of burnout respectively while low levels of burnout was found among 45 (40.2%) and 47(42.0%) respectively. Overall, burnout in all the three subscales was found to among 11 (9.8%) of the resident doctors in training. Table 2

At binary logistic regression analysis level, the odds of burn out among the resident doctors was found to be 1.36 times for every one-year increase in the duration of training (95% CI: 1.001 – 1.851; $p = 0.049$). Similarly, at the multivariable logistic regression model, the odds of burnout was 1.60 times (95% CI: 1.107– 2.313; $p = 0.012$) for every one year increase in the duration of residency training having adjusted for other factors such as age, sex, marital status, department of specialty, number of call duty taken per month, estimated hours worked per day and number of posting rotations ever done. Table 3

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents

Characteristics	Frequency (n = 112)	Percentage
Age (years)		
= 34 years	67	59.8
35 years and above	45	40.2
Mean Age	Mean \pm SD 34.0 \pm 4.3 years	
Sex		
Female	27	24.1
Male	85	75.9
Marital status		
Married	68	60.7
Single	44	39.2
Religion		
Christianity	104	92.9
Islam	5	4.5
Others*	3	2.7
Number of years in Residency Training		
= 3	80	71.4
4 and more	32	28.6
Median (IQR)	2.5 (1- 4) years	
Department of training		
Medicine related	74	66.1
Surgery related	38	33.9
Number of calls taken in a month		
= 3	37	33.0
4 and above	75	67.0
Median (IQR)	4 (2- 6)	
Minimum hours worked per day		
= 8	95	84.5
9 and above	17	15.2
Mean	Mean \pm SD 8.7 \pm 2.6	
Number of posting rotations ever done		
= 4	86	76.8
5 and above	26	23.2
Median (IQR)	1 (0 – 5)	

SD = Standard Deviation, IQR = Interquartile range, *= Atheists, Agnostics, African traditional worshippers

Table 2: Level of Burnout among the respondents

Burnout Subscale	Frequency (n=112)	Percentage
Emotional Exhaustion		
Low level	66	58.9
Moderate level	36	32.2
High level	10	8.9
Depersonalization		
Low level		
Moderate level	45	40.2
High level	35	31.3
	32	28.5
Personal Accomplishment		
Low level	47	42.0
Moderate level	26	23.2
High level	39	34.8
Burnout in all the subscales		
Yes	11	9.8
No	101	90.2
Subscale Scores	Median (IQR)	
Emotional Exhaustion subscale	16 (8 –21)	
Depersonalization subscale	7 (3 – 12)	
Personal Accomplishment subscale	38 (29 – 42)	

IQR=Interquartile Range

Table 3: Multiple Logistic Regression of Predictors of Burnout among the respondents

Factors	COR (95%CI)	P - value	AOR (95% CI)	P – value*
Age (years)	0.95 (0.817 – 1.114)	0.551	0.82 (0.654 – 1.039)	0.099
Sex				
Female	0.29 (0.035 – 2.364)	0.247	0.22 (0.020 – 2.365)	0.209
Male	1 -		1 -	-
Marital Status				
Married	1.15 (0.315 – 4.175)	0.835	1.69 (0.329 – 8.635)	0.531
Single	1 -		1 -	-
Years in Residency	1.36 (1.001 – 1.851)	0.049*	1.60 (1.107– 2.313)	0.012*
Department of specialty				
Medicine related	1.41 (0.353 – 5.670)	0.625	3.75 (0.579 – 23.555)	0.159
Surgery related	1 -		1 -	-
Number of calls taken per month	1.12 (0.963 – 1.293)	0.146	1.17 (0.970 – 1.405)	0.101
Hours worked per day	1.04 (0.840 – 1.276)	0.747	1.05 (0.798 – 1.385)	0.721
Number of posting rotations ever done	0.93 (0.777 – 1.122)	0.467	0.94 (0.747 – 1.171)	0.561

COR = Crude Odds Ratio, AOR = Adjusted Odds Ratio, * = Statistically significant

Discussion

Burnout is a phenomenon characterized by emotional exhaustion (EE) expressed as feelings of tiredness and emptiness, depersonalization (DP) manifesting as a state of lack of empathy, increased levels of cynicism and automatism as well as lack of personal accomplishment (PA) which is a reflection of lack of self-esteem and increased levels of frustration.^{15,18} In this study, the prevalence of burnout using a combination of the three subscales was found in about a tenth of the resident doctors while high level of EE was reported in about a tenth of the resident doctors. Furthermore, almost a third had high level of burnout on the DP subscale and slightly below half had low level of personal achievement. These findings have shared similarities with what was reported by other studies conducted in Nigeria, Oman and China.^{3,15,19} These similarities could be attributable to the fact that similar study design and tool of assessment of burnout were used as well these studies being conducted in similar

context. However, other studies carried out in the Nigeria, Indian, Malaysia, Switzerland and the United States of America reported a much higher overall levels of burnt out as well as subscale specific burnout rates.^{7,20,21,22,23,24,25,26} This variation may be hinged on the fact that some of the studies used different burn out assessment methods such as Mini -Z single item, different burnout categorization technique as well as different study designs. However, it is imperative to state that the levels of burn out reported by this study and other related studies are high and not acceptable if productively will be enhanced and positive treatment outcomes are desired regardless of the context and concept used. The implication of these findings to the practice of public and occupational health is that if health care providers are emotionally exhausted, depersonalized, physical fatigued and low on personal achievement rating, treatment outcomes of their clients may be negative impacted while a higher tendency of occurrence of self-harm is also a possibility among

these health care providers.

In this study, increasing duration of training was found to be the sole driver of burnout which has also been reported by other studies. However, these other studies also reported other factors such as excess workload, length of stay in a position, long working hours, increasing age, sex, practicing in a tertiary health institution and differing specialties being reported.^{3,15,19,20,21,23,24,27}

This has brought to light the fact that regardless of the settings or regions of practice, burnout among medical doctors is common and is driven by increasing duration in training. Therefore, it is important to be context specific in addressing the issue of burnout among medical doctors in order to achieve sustainable results and promote a healthy workplace.

Conclusion

This study has brought to light the level of burn out among resident doctors with duration of time in training being the main driver of burnout. Therefore, it will be imperative to centre interventions targeted at addressing burnout among residents around the duration of time in training in order to achieve optimal results.

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Data availability

Data are available from the corresponding author at reasonable request.

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